

Reactions of Lead Halides in Molten Potassium Nitrite. Action of Dinitrogen Tetroxide and its Thermal Dissociation Products on Lead Halides. A New Method for Accurate Determination of Iodides in Presence of Chloride and Bromide

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The reactions of lead halides (chloride, bromide and iodide) in molten potassium nitrite has been investigated in highly evacuated all glass system. It has been observed that though nitrogen dioxide, nitric oxide and dinitrogen trioxide are all evolved during the reaction, none of them react with the chloride and bromide salts forming nitrosyl chloride or nitrosyl bromide. In the case of the reaction with iodide too, no nitrosyl iodide is formed; but instead free iodine is knocked out in the elemental state. The reactions have also been carried out in vacuum to study the action of pure dinitrogen tetroxide and its thermal dissociation products on lead chloride, lead bromide and lead iodide. It has been found that no reaction took place on treatment of the tetroxide with the chloride and bromide salts, while quantitative reaction took place with the iodide giving free iodine and not nitrosyl iodide. The ease with which iodine was knocked out from ionic iodide by nitrogen dioxide or trioxide suggested an interesting method to estimate iodine of ionic iodide by means of nitrogen dioxide dissolved in organic solvent.

It has been observed¹ that both potassium and sodium nitrites form clear liquid melt in vacuum at their melting points. But no reaction of salts in these melts have ever been investigated. The work has been undertaken to find the behaviour of lead halides (chloride, bromide and iodide) in molten potassium nitrite. The reactions were carried out in order to find out whether nitrosyl halide was ever formed in the reaction since method has been suggested² to prepare pure nitrosyl chloride from moist potassium chloride and dinitrogen tetroxide. In the present case as at the temperature of reactions gaseous products namely nitric oxide, dinitrogen trioxide and nitrogen dioxide are invariably formed, it is interesting to note that these gases do not react with any ionic halides except with iodides. Hence, the experimental work was also undertaken to study the action of dinitrogen tetroxide and its thermal dissociation products on lead chloride, lead bromide, lead iodide and also on potassium chloride, potassium bromide and potassium iodide. As dinitrogen tetroxide is quite soluble in many organic solvents like carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, ethyl acetate etc., the reactions of the above mentioned salts with the tetroxide dissolved in organic solvents were also studied.

The study yields a method for the quantitative determination of iodide in presence of chloride and bromide.

Experimental

The experimental technique (all glass blown apparatus) to study the reaction of lead halides in molten

potassium nitrite was essentially the same as used by Oza and Oza³. In some experiments potassium nitrite was taken in large excess but a constant quantity in molar proportion to lead halides (varying mass) than required for the reaction to be quantitative, while in some experiments excess of lead halides (constant mass) in molar proportion to potassium nitrite (varying mass) required for the reaction to be quantitative, was taken. It was necessary to note exact temperature at which reactions were carried out because once potassium nitrite melts it remains in molten state at all temperatures beyond its melting point. For this purpose the help of mercury level of manometer attached to the sprenzel pump was taken because it always attended the constant height when full vacuum in the system was created. The heating in the electric furnace was done carefully after 200° so that sufficient time takes place for rise of ten degree centigrade. At this moment mercury level in the manometer was carefully watched. It was found that at 280° slight fall in height of mercury level was indicated; but rate of fall was very slow indicating that the reaction just started. It was appreciable at 300° and hence this temperature was fixed with range of $\pm 10^\circ$. The heating was discontinued as soon as fall in height of mercury column attended a constant value and when no further release of bubble from alkali bulb was noticed. The gaseous product of the reaction was pumped off as usual by working the sprenziel pump. The alkali lye was collected and diluted to known volume by distilled water. It was analysed first qualitatively for detection of nitrite, nitrate and halide ions and then quantitatively

for the ions actually detected. In not a single experiment halide was ever detected in alkali solution. Even when iodine was knocked out as an element, it was accumulated as solid in cooler part of the system; and iodine vapour never entered the alkali solution. The solid residue at the end of each experiment was carefully weighed and treated with water. In case of experiments with lead iodide it was treated with carbon tetrachloride in order to dissolve free iodine. The residue was treated with water and the soluble extracts were diluted to known volume. Insoluble material was dried and weighed. It was dissolved in 2*N* potassium hydroxide solution where it was found to be completely soluble. The water extract was first qualitatively analysed to detect the presence of nitrite, nitrate and halide ions, alkalinity and lead ions. The test for alkalinity was performed in order to detect the formation of potassium plumbate if any formed in the reaction. The insoluble residue which was dissolved in 2*N* alkali was analysed for its lead content. The amount of lead thus found was exactly equivalent to lead in lead oxide formed in reaction. The water soluble extract never contained nitrate except in case of experiments with lead iodide wherein only qualitative test was appreciable, but the amount being so less, it was not possible to estimate it. From the literature cited⁴ it has been found that potassium iodide reacts with nitrogen dioxide according to the following equation

In order to study the action of dinitrogen tetroxide and its thermal dissociation products on lead halides and potassium iodide, the apparatus and the technique used was the same as in Oza and Oza and Thaker⁵. Dinitrogen tetroxide and its thermal dissociation products do not react with lead chloride and lead bromide when treated for half an hour or one hour upto all the temperatures ranging from 0° to 300°. However, it reacted very easily at 0° upto 250° with lead iodide and potassium iodide almost quantitatively. The ease with which iodide was knocked out from the molecule of iodide especially the ionic iodide in contact with the oxides of nitrogen suggested a method to determine iodine content of iodide by use of dinitrogen tetroxide dissolved in organic solvent. The procedure adopted to prepare a solution of dinitrogen tetroxide in organic solvent was essentially the same as adopted by Oza⁶.

The tubes containing dinitrogen tetroxide liquid were broken open in carbon tetrachloride, chloroform or ethyl acetate in which large amount of the gas was found soluble. In ordinary dry test tube a known weight of sodium iodide or potassium iodide (finely crushed and dried) was taken and the organic liquid containing dissolved dinitrogen tetroxide was added and shaken carefully. Iodine was immediately knocked out from the iodide by nitrogen dioxide or dinitrogen tetroxide and remained in dissolved condition in organic solvent. If the solvent was carbon tetrachloride or chloroform it immediately turned violet in colour. It was repeatedly extracted with

further quantity of above solvent containing dinitrogen tetroxide till the extract did not show any colour due to iodine. These extracts were allowed to be kept at 30° when all the nitrogen dioxide fumes were removed completely. This was done in fuming cupboard. The iodine content of the solution was determined by titration with standard thiosulphate without using indicator. The insoluble residue after the above treatment was washed twice by dry acetone or ether and dried in oven at 70° for half an hour and weighed. It was dissolved out in water and the solution was made to known volume. It was analysed qualitatively for nitrite, nitrate and iodide ions but only positive test was given for nitrate ion. The solution was quantitatively analysed for determining nitrate by standard method⁷. The experiments were done by adding known weight of chloride and bromide alone or in admixture with each other, but only iodine was determined accurately without slightest interference. Slight difficulty was encountered when the solvent used to dissolve dinitrogen tetroxide was ethyl acetate. This solvent has great potentiality to retain dinitrogen tetroxide and hence it becomes difficult to remove it. But this difficulty was overcome by keeping solution at 25° and bubbling dry carbon dioxide or nitrogen through it and thus all dinitrogen tetroxide was completely removed. The solution was then estimated by thiosulphate till decolouration of brown colour.

Results and Discussion

The results of experiments with lead halides are given in Table 1. Those with dinitrogen tetroxide and its thermal dissociation products in Table 2, and those with dinitrogen tetroxide in organic solvent in Table 3. The reaction with lead chloride and lead bromide goes according to the following equations:

and NO_2 evolved does not react with KCl, KBr or even with PbCl_2 and PbBr_2 .

The reaction of lead iodide with potassium nitrite in molten state seems to be proceeding according to the following equation

and lead nitrite formed reacts immediately with molten lead iodide according to the following equation to form free iodine

Very little nitrate seems to have been formed in this reaction due to slight decomposition of $\text{Pb(NO}_2)_2$ according to equation (iii), and nitrogen dioxide evolved

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TABLE I

(a) System : $PbCl_2 + KNO_2$ Temperature : 300°

Expt. No.	Time (mins.)	Wt. of KNO_2 taken, mg.	Wt. of PbX_2 taken, mg.	Wt. of residue formed, mg.	PbX_2 left unreacted, mg	KNO_2 left unreacted, mg.	PbO formed, mg.	Nitric-oxide(NO) evolved at N.T.P., ml.	NO_2 evolved at N.T.P., ml.	Nitrogen N_2 evolved at N.T.P., ml.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1	30	341.0	55.00	383.10	0.000	305.4	46.8	4.70	4.71	0.20
		40.13×10^{-4}	1.979×10^{-4}			35.93×10^{-4}	2.096×10^{-4}	2.086×10^{-4}	2.098×10^{-4}	
2	35	340.0	139.0	450.90	0.000	246.8	122.3	13.2	13.2	0.30
		40.00×10^{-4}	5.0×10^{-4}			29.0×10^{-4}	5.48×10^{-4}	5.89×10^{-4}	5.89×10^{-4}	
3	30	340.0	278.0	539.7	0.000	172.3	220.3	22.1	22.1	0.20
		40.0×10^{-4}	10×10^{-4}			20.27×10^{-4}	9.87×10^{-4}	9.86×10^{-4}	9.86×10^{-4}	
4	35	170.0	278.0	390.0	66.0	41.00	170.0	17.0	17.0	0.30
		20.0×10^{-4}	10.0×10^{-4}		2.374×10^{-4}	4.82×10^{-4}	7.61×10^{-4}	7.58×10^{-4}	7.58×10^{-4}	
5	40	98.5	278.0	275.4	180.0	25.0	17.87	7.9	7.9	0.2
		10.0×10^{-4}	10.0×10^{-4}		6.47×10^{-4}	2.94×10^{-4}	0.800×10^{-4}	3.52×10^{-4}	3.52×10^{-4}	
6	20	42.0	278.0	301.4	210.0	nil	54.80	5.5	5.5	0.1
		4.94×10^{-4}	10.0×10^{-4}		7.55×10^{-4}	nil	2.45×10^{-4}	2.45×10^{-4}	2.45×10^{-4}	

(b) System : $PbBr_2 + KNO_2$ Temperature : 300°

Expt. No.	Time (mins.)	Wt. of KNO_2 taken, mg.	Wt. of PbX_2 taken, mg.	Wt. of residue formed, mg.	PbX_2 left unreacted, mg	KNO_2 left unreacted, mg.	PbO formed, mg.	Nitric-oxide(NO) evolved at N.T.P., ml.	NO_2 evolved at N.T.P., ml.	Nitrogen N_2 evolved at N.T.P., ml.
7	37	340.0	36.0	369.0	11.40	330.9	14.95	1.50	1.50	0.1
		40×10^{-4}	0.98×10^{-4}		0.310×10^{-4}	38.9×10^{-4}	0.669×10^{-4}	0.669×10^{-4}	0.669×10^{-4}	
8	30	340.0	73.0	401.0	18.9	315.0	32.89	3.3	3.3	0.2
		40×10^{-4}	1.988×10^{-4}		0.514×10^{-4}	37.0×10^{-4}	1.47×10^{-4}	1.47×10^{-4}	1.47×10^{-4}	
9	45	340.0	11.0	433.75	31.3	303.6	37.83	4.8	4.8	0.3
		40×10^{-4}	2.99×10^{-4}		0.852×10^{-4}	35.72×10^{-4}	2.14×10^{-4}	2.14×10^{-4}	2.14×10^{-4}	
10	55	171.0	367.0	519.9	280.0	130.8	52.8	5.30	5.30	0.1
		20.12×10^{-4}	9.99×10^{-4}		7.62×10^{-4}	15.38×10^{-4}	2.36×10^{-4}	2.36×10^{-4}	2.36×10^{-4}	
11	40	85.0	368.0	508.9	210.6	99.0	98.65	9.90	9.9	0.2
		10×10^{-4}	10.02×10^{-4}		5.61×10^{-4}	1.16×10^{-4}	4.42×10^{-4}	4.42×10^{-4}	4.4×10^{-4}	
12	25	42.0	368.0	609.38	327.0	23.08	25.02	2.50	2.50	0.1
		4.94×10^{-4}	10.02×10^{-4}		8.9×10^{-4}	2.71×10^{-4}	2.12×10^{-4}	1.116×10^{-4}	1.1×10^{-4}	

(c) System : $PbI_2 + KNO_2$ Temperature : 300°

Expt. No.	Time (mins.)	Wt. of KNO_2 taken, mg.	Wt. of PbX_2 taken, mg.	Wt. of residue formed, mg.	PbX_2 left unreacted, mg	KNO_2 left unreacted, mg.	PbO formed, mg.	Nitric-oxide(NO) evolved at N.T.P., ml.	NO_2 evolved at N.T.P., ml.	Nitrogen N_2 evolved at N.T.P., ml.
13	30	340.0	56.0	508.0	10.7	331.5	21.93	2.20	2.20	12.47
		40.0×10^{-4}	1.21×10^{-4}		0.232×10^{-4}	38.99×10^{-4}	0.98×10^{-4}	0.98×10^{-4}	0.98×10^{-4}	0.49×10^{-4}
14	25	342.0	112.0	554.0	11.0	323.9	48.89	4.90	4.90	27.78
		40.2×10^{-4}	2.42×10^{-4}		0.238×10^{-4}	38.11×10^{-4}	2.18×10^{-4}	2.18×10^{-4}	2.18×10^{-4}	1.09×10^{-4}
15	50	341.0	226.0	512.4	41.0	306.9	89.69	9.0	9.0	51.02
		40.1×10^{-4}	4.90×10^{-4}		0.38×10^{-4}	35.30×10^{-4}	4.01×10^{-4}	4.01×10^{-4}	4.01×10^{-4}	2.0×10^{-4}
16	50	8.00	331.0	—	269.2	NIH	29.89	2.20	2.20	12.47
		0.94×10^{-4}	7.17×10^{-4}		5.83×10^{-4}		1.339×10^{-4}	0.98×10^{-4}	0.98×10^{-4}	0.49×10^{-4}
17	38	17.0	331.0	310.4	240.7	2.00	38.87	3.9	3.9	22.12
		2.0×10^{-4}	7.17×10^{-4}		5.21×10^{-4}	0.235×10^{-4}	1.74×10^{-4}	1.74×10^{-4}	1.74×10^{-4}	0.87×10^{-4}
18	22	34.00	331.0	308.6	166.0	3.60	79.7	8.0	8.0	45.36
		4.00×10^{-4}	7.17×10^{-4}		3.54×10^{-4}	0.423×10^{-4}	2.570×10^{-4}	3.57×10^{-4}	3.57×10^{-4}	1.78×10^{-4}

TABLE 2—REACTIONS OF SOME IODIDES WITH N_2O_4 IN VACUUM.

A : System : $PbI_2 + N_2O_4$

Expt. No.	Temp. °C	Time min.	Wt. of Iodine taken, mg.	Wt. of N_2O_4 taken, mg.	Wt. of residue found, mg.	Wt. of Iodide left, mg.	Wt. of Nitrate formed, mg.	Wt. of N_2O_4 left, mg.	Wt. of N_2O_4 formed, mg.	Volume of 'NO' liberated, ml.	Wt. of Iodine liberated, mg.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1	0	30	53.0 1.14×10^{-4}	265.0 28.8×10^{-4}	63.00	7.90 0.17×10^{-4}	30.3 0.91×10^{-4}	248.0 26.96×10^{-4}	7.00 0.91×10^{-4}	nil	24.8 0.97×10^{-4}
2	0	45	55.0 1.19×10^{-4}	55.3 6.01×10^{-4}	68.6	4.1 0.088×10^{-4}	36.67 1.1×10^{-4}	35.0 3.8×10^{-4}	—	4.9 2.18×10^{-4}	28.0 1.1×10^{-4}
3	30	45	60.00 1.302×10^{-4}	101.5 11.04×10^{-4}	73.0	9.1 0.197×10^{-4}	36.65 1.108×10^{-4}	81.3 8.83×10^{-4}	—	4.9 2.18×10^{-4}	27.8 1.19×10^{-4}
4	30	55	75.0 1.628×10^{-4}	112.4 12.2×10^{-4}	81.0	5.6 0.121×10^{-4}	49.0 1.48×10^{-4}	84.8 9.21×10^{-4}	—	6.7 2.49×10^{-4}	27.0 1.45×10^{-4}
5	100	65	70.0 1.51×10^{-4}	123.5 13.4×10^{-4}	88.0	nil	50.0 1.511×10^{-4}	95.9 1.64×10^{-4}	0.85 0.109×10^{-4}	6.7 2.99×10^{-4}	38.2 1.45×10^{-4}
6	150	45	100.0 2.169×10^{-4}	135.3 15.76×10^{-4}	122.0	75. 0.162×10^{-4}	63.5 1.91×10^{-4}	98.3 11.45×10^{-4}	—	9.0 4.012×10^{-4}	51.6 2.03×10^{-4}
7	250	35	100.2 2.173×10^{-4}	146.5 15.9×10^{-4}	126.0	nil	70.0 2.114×10^{-4}	106.1 11.53×10^{-4}	0.80 0.1053×10^{-4}	9.8 4.37×10^{-4}	56.4 2.20×10^{-4}

(b) System : $KI + N_2O_4$

8	0	80	50.5 3.049×10^{-4}	310.0 33.7×10^{-4}	72.0	0.4 0.24×10^{-4}	32.0 3.168×10^{-4}	267.0 29.0×10^{-4}	24.0 3.15×10^{-4}	—	40.0 1.515×10^{-4}
9	100	70	65.0 3.91×10^{-4}	115.0 12.5×10^{-4}	89.0	3.0 0.180×10^{-4}	38.0 3.76×10^{-4}	80.6 8.76×10^{-4}	—	8.4 3.75×10^{-4}	48.5 1.909×10^{-4}
10	250	75	105.0 6.32×10^{-4}	135.0 14.6×10^{-4}	142.0	nil	62.7 6.203×10^{-4}	77.5 8.42×10^{-4}	—	14.0 6.062×10^{-4}	80.0 3.15×10^{-4}

TABLE 3. REACTIONS OF SOME IODIDES WITH N_2O_4 DISSOLVED IN AN ORGANIC SOLVENT

(a) System :

Expt. No.	Weight of iodide taken, mg.	Weight of KCl added, mg.	Weight of KBr added, mg.	Weight of iodide determined, mg.	Weight of nitrate formed as found by titration, mg.	Weight of N_2O_4 dissolved in organic solvent, mg.
1.	45.0	nil	nil	44.8	27.1	256.5
2.	50.0	nil	nil	49.8	30.2	270.0
3.	55.0	nil	nil	55.6	33.8	321.5
4.	57.8	15.0	20.0	58.0	35.0	266.5
5.	65.4	20.0	nil	66.0	39.8	344.5
6.	67.3	nil	20.0	67.3	40.9	277.5
7.	74.6	30.0	nil	75.5	45.5	286.5
8.	83.2	nil	25.0	82.9	50.5	248.5
9.	200.0	nil	nil	199.0	126.0	688.0

(b) System :

10.	51.0	nil	nil	52.0	33.1	130.0
11.	207.0	nil	nil	203.0	—	—

(c) System :

12.	50.0	nil	nil	48.0	35.8	235.0
13.	70.0	nil	nil	69.0	46.8	249.0

reacting with potassium iodide according to the following equation

That the reaction proceeds according to equation (V) is proved from the fact that solid residue gives only faint qualitative test for nitrate ion and this nitrate might have been formed by reaction No. (VI).

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